

Location of the restorer gene *Rf3* on chromosome 1. The map was developed using the *F*₂ population of 36 sterile plants derived from the cross Zhenshan 97 A/ZSR21. Molecular markers are shown on the right side of the figure. Map distances (in cM) are based on the Kosambi function.

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Characterization of common *cis*-regulatory elements responsible for endosperm-specific expression of rice glutelin gene

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Glutelin is the major seed storage protein of rice, accounting for about 80% of total endosperm protein. Since glutelin genes are expressed only in maturing endosperm tissue and are regulated mainly at the transcriptional level, they provide excellent

model systems of regulation of tissue-specific gene expression.

Glutelin is coded for by a small multi-gene family composed of about 10 copies per haploid genome (Okita et al 1989, Takaiwa and Oono 1991, Takaiwa et al 1991). These genes are clearly classified into two groups—designated as GluA and GluB subfamilies—that share about 60-65% homology between members of each subfamily at the nucleotide sequence level (Takaiwa et al 1991). Comparison of the nucleotide sequence in the 5' flanking regions of six glutelin genes showed that the conserved sequences are restricted to the 13 bp of AACA motif around -70, the GCN4 motif around -160 and -90, and the GCAA motif around -350 from the transcriptional start site. Therefore, these motifs may be candidate for *cis*-regulatory elements controlling the endosperm-specific expression found in the glutelin genes.

To identify the common *cis*-regulatory elements responsible for the endosperm-specific expression of glutelin genes, the 5' and 3' nested deletions and internal deletions of the 5' flanking regions of the *GluB-1* and *GluA-3* genes were transcriptionally fused to either β -glucuronidase (GUS) or firefly luciferase (LUX) reporter genes. These chimeric genes were transferred into the tobacco genome via *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation system or into the rice genome using electroporation method. The GUS or LUX activities were assayed in maturing seeds.

The GUS reporter gene was expressed at high levels in the sub-aleurone layer of the maturing rice seed. Essential *cis*-regulatory elements governing the spatially and temporally specific expression of the glutelin genes were located within the first 437 bp and 245 bp of the promoter regions of the *GluA-3* and *GluB-1* genes, respectively (Yoshihara and Takaiwa 1995).

The AACA motif and the GCNA4 motif within the 100 bp of the 5' flanking region, common to all the glutelin genes, were the key elements determining endosperm-specific expression of glutelin genes. Deletion or site-specific mutagenesis of this proximal AACA motif remarkably reduced

promoter activities. The GCN4 motif also acted as a major *cis*-regulatory element determining the quantitative level. Each of these elements is necessary, but not sufficient, for endosperm-specific expression because tissue specificity is retained irrespective of the absence of each element. However, deleting the entire region, which includes both the AACA and GCN4 motifs, abolished seed-specific expression, suggesting that the synergistic interaction between both elements determines the endosperm-specific expression of the glutelin genes.

To confirm the significance of combining the AACA and GCN4 motifs to confer the endosperm-specific expression, the regions (-245 to -145, -113 to -40), including both motifs, were fused to the truncated (-90 to +9) or core (-46 to +1) CaMV35S promoter/GUS cassette, and then introduced into tobacco and rice. Although neither the AACA motif nor the GCN4 motif—by itself—is capable of enhancing the truncated promoter of CaMV35S promoter, their combination conferred the endosperm-specific expression. However, the combination failed to activate promoter activity of the core CaMV promoter.

The results suggest that the combination of two sets of AACA and GCN4 motifs or the combination of one set of these two motifs and the G-box motif is required for the endosperm-specific expression of the rice glutelin gene.

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